

Procedure :

Vosburg and Cooper's² method was employed for knowing the number of complexes formed in the case of Cu(II). The plot of optical densities against wavelength gave a maximum at 430 m μ thereby showing the existense of only one complex.

The composition was determined by Job's method⁴ of continued variation as well as by the molar ratio method. For Job's method equimolar solutions of the metal and the chelating agent were mixed in different metal to reagent ratio and their absorbance measured against 70% alcohol as blank.

For the molar ratio method⁵, solution were prepared with a constant concentration of copper but with the varying ratio of the moles of the chelating agent to the moles of copper. The absorbance of these solutions were measured against 70% alcohol as blank. The curves show a sharp breaks at the molar ratio 1 : 2 as metal; chelating agent

Conductometric studies :

Both direct (cupric nitrate in the cell) and reverse N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine in the cell titrations were performed at different concentration of the reactants sharp inflection point were obtained at the stoichiometric ratio) Cu : N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 2.

Composition of insoluble complexes of Hg(II), Mo(VI) and W(VI) conductometric studies :

Both direct (mercuric chloride, amm. molybdate and sodium tungstate in the cell) and reverse N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine in the cell titrations were performed at different concentrations of the reactants. Sharp inflection points were obtained at the stoichiometric ratio corresponding Hg : M-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 2, Mo : N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 1 and W : N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 1.

Amperometric studies :

Amperometric titrations N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine and mercuric chloride were carried out using sodium fluoride (1M) as supporting electrolyte and 0.01% gelatin as maxima suppressar at a potential of -0.05 volt (obtained from the plateau of the polarograph of mercuric chloride).

Amperometric titrations between N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine and ammonium molybdate or sodium tungstate were carried out using HCl (0.05M) as supporting electrolyte at a potential -1.0 and -0.8 volt for ammonium molybdate and sodium tungstate respectively.

Direct (mercuric chloride, ammonium molybdate and sodium tungstate in the cell) and reverse (N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine in the cell) titration reveal the existence of 1 : 2 complex in case of Hg(II) and 1 : 1 in the case of Mo(VI) and W(VI) respectively.

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An attempted synthesis of Schmid's 2-Methyl-10-Methoxy- β -Brazanquinone

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THE paper describes the synthesis of 3,10-dimethoxy- β -brazanquinone(V) employing Bentley and Robinson's method¹ and an attempt to utilize the reaction sequence for the synthesis of Schmid's 2-methyl-10-methoxy- β -brazanquinone^{2,3}. Thus, 1,3-dimethoxybenzene was condensed with *o*-methoxyphenylacetic acid to the hydroxyketone (I), which was then transformed into the corresponding phenoxyester (II). The phenoxyester then under went a smooth cyclization in presence of sodium methoxide to methyl-6-methoxy-3-(2'-methoxy)-benzyl coumarone-2-carboxylate(III), the latter upon hydrolysis and intramolecular cyclization afforded 3,10-dimethoxy-6-hydroxy- β -brazan(IV). Oxidation of hydroxybrazan with chromic acid gave the desired quinone(V).

However, adaption of this route for the synthesis of Schmid's quinone presented serious difficulties at an early stage. Thus, the desired benzyl ketone could not be obtained in the pure form by condensing *p*-cresylmethyl ester with *o*-methoxyphenylacetic chloride. Although a crude product was obtained giving the expected colour reactions, the compound could not be purified for further studies.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and were determined in pyrex capillaries. IR spectra has been recorded on Perkin-Elmer infraoord model 237 in potassium bromide.

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl-(2'-methoxy)-benzyl ketone (I) :

o-Methoxyphenylacetic acid (2.75 g.) was converted into acid chloride by treatment with thionyl chloride (5 ml.) in dry carbon disulphide. This was then added to anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.2 g.) with cooling. A brown complex soon formed. At this stage, freshly distilled 1,3-dimethoxybenzene (2.1 ml.) in 5 ml. dry carbon disulphide was added. The mixture was then heated on steam-bath for 2.5 hr., cooled and worked up in the usual manner.

NOTES

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl-(2'-methoxy)-benzyl ketone (I, 2.2) g. crystallized out from benzene in white prisms, m.p. 93°-5° (Found C : 70.4; H : 6.1 C₁₆H₁₆O₄ reqd. C : 70.6; H : 5.9%). 2,4-DNP was crystallized from ethyl acetate in red prisms, m.p. 179°-81° (Found N : 12.2 C₂₂H₂₀O₇N₄ reqd. N : 12.4%).

2-(Methoxycarbonylthioxy)-4-methoxyphenyl-(2'-methoxy) benzyl ketone (II) :

The foregoing ketone (3.5 g.) was dissolved in acetone (35 ml.) to which was added potassium carbonate (11.5 g.), followed by ethylbromoacetate (1.7 ml.). The mixture was then refluxed gently on steam-bath for 6 hr. and cooled. Organic layer was filtered out and the residue washed with 2 × 10 ml. portions of boiling acetone. On distilling off acetone, a red oil was obtained, which solidified on standing to a white solid (2.7 g.). It crystallized from ethanol in long white needles, m.p. 99°-100° (Found C : 66.9; H : 6.2 C₂₀H₂₂O₆ reqd. C : 67.0; H : 6.2%).

Methyl-6-methoxy-3(2'-methoxy)-benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylate (III) :

Freshly cut sodium (0.05 g.) was dissolved in absolute methanol (29 ml.). When the mixture has cooled down to room temperature, phenoxy keto-ester (0.56 g.) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. and then poured into water. A white gummy mass separated, which was extracted with 3 × 5 ml. portions of benzene. Benzene extract on concentration and cooling gave white needles of the ester (III, yield 0.25 g.). The ester was crystallized from methanol in short needles, m.p.

62°-71° (Found C, 69.8; H, 5.6 C₁₉H₁₈O₅ reqd. C, 69.9; H, 5.6%).

The aqueous layer was concentrated to a small volume and left in the refrigerator for sometime, whereby a white solid (0.07 g.) m.p. 180°-83°, was obtained. This compound was soluble in alkali and evolved carbon dioxide in contact with bicarbonate.

3,10-Dimethoxy-6-hydroxy-β-braza (IV) :

Methyl ester (III, 0.3 g.) was refluxed on steam-bath for 45 min. with methanolic potassium hydroxide (10 ml., 10%) and then excess methanol was distilled off. The residue was dissolved in water acidified the aqueous solution to get the corresponding acid (0.28 g., m.p. 190°-92°, in shining plates from acetic acid). Mixed m.p. with a crystallized sample of acid obtained above, was undepressed. (Found : C, 69.2; H, 5.0 C₁₈H₁₆O₅ reqd. C, 69.2; H, 5.2%).

The foregoing acid (0.3 g.) was suspended in dry carbon disulphide (15 ml.). To this added thionyl chloride (0.2 ml.), heated for 4 hr. on steam-bath and worked up in the usual manner to obtain 3,10-dimethoxy-6-hydroxy-β-braza (IV 0.25 g., m.p. 260°-65°). Due to its impure nature, the compound could not be analyzed.

Oxidation : The crude hydroxy-β-braza (0.4 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (6 ml.) and was added to chromic acid (0.05 g.). After the initial exothermic reaction ceased, it was refluxed for a few minute and cooled. Water was added to precipitate the brazaquinone (V). Since no solid

Fig. 1

separated, it was extracted with 3 × 5 ml portions of chloroform and concentrated to 5 ml. The concentrated solution (golden-yellow) was chromatographed over alumina. The first fraction, pale yellow, in colour, furnished the desired quinone (0.2 g., m.p. 240°–41° from acetic acid in orange coloured needles. Found C, 70.4; H, 4.0 C₁₈H₁₂O₅ reqd. C, 70.1; H, 3.9%. IR spectrum, 6.02 and 6.19μ [1,4-quinone]; 6.78, 7.44, 8.03, 8.33 and 8.81μ [methoxy group]).

Attempted synthesis of (6-hydroxy-3-methyl)-phenyl (2'-methoxy)-benzyl ketone :

o-Methoxyphenylacetic acid (1.5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (10 ml.) and thionyl chloride (3 ml.) was added to it. The acid chloride thus obtained was added to cold of ether (5 ml.) containing anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.66 g.) Freshly distilled *p*-cresylmethyl ether (1.1 g.) in dry ether (5 ml.) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 7 hr. and the product was decomposed in the usual manner, when a crystalline solid (0.08 g., m.p. 88°), was obtained. The product thus obtained gave a greyish-violet ferric reaction, but was alkali insoluble and failed to form a 2,4-DNP. However, the compound could not be obtained in analytically pure form.

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**Studies on Potential Pesticides—Part II
Synthesis of N-(2-Mercapto acetyl)-5-amino-
(substituted-aryl)-1,3,4 thiadiazolyl hydrazides
and N'-[(2-Mercapto acetyl)-5-amino substituted-aryl]-1,3,4 thiadiazolyl]-N⁴-
(phenyl)-3-semicarbazide**

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THIADIAZOLES and related compounds have found to possess biological activity in recent years¹⁻³. 2-Arylamino-5-mercapto thiadiazoles were shown to be pesticidal and fungicidal agents by

Giri *et al.*⁴ and Sen Gupta *et al.*⁵. Various hydroxides have been reported as antibacterial⁶ and fungicidal⁷ compounds. Gahon *et al.*⁸ have shown various semicarbazides to be more poisonous to caterpillars and other insects than deris dust. With a view to investigate the properties of compounds with these moieties we have synthesized several thiadiazoles. 2-Mercapto-5-arylamino 1,3,4-thiadiazoles were prepared by the cyclisation of aryl amino thiosemicarbazides. 2-Mercapto-5-amino (substituted aryl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl ethyl acetates were synthesized by the condensation of above thiadiazoles with chloro ethyl acetate. Hydrazides of the above esters were prepared and condensed with phenyl isocyanate to obtain the required semicarbazides.

Experimental

(All melting points are uncorrected).

Preparation of 2-Mercapto-5-amino (substituted aryl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl ethyl acetates :

A mixture of 2-Aryl amino-5-mercapto thiadiazole⁹⁻¹⁰ (0.01 mole), sodium hydroxide (0.01 mole) and chloro ethyl acetate (0.01 mole) in ethanol was heated on water bath for 2 hr. The product which was obtained by pouring the mixture in water was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol

The m.p., analytical data, yield are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analytical data %	
					Found	Reqd.
1. Hydrogen		91	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 48.46	48.81
					H 4.18	4.41
					N 14.06	14.24
2. 2-Methyl		60	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 49.88	50.49
					H 4.21	4.85
					N 13.43	13.59
3. 3-Methyl		120	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 49.65	50.49
					H 4.24	4.85
					N 13.63	13.59
4. 4-Methyl		96	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 50.18	50.49
					H 4.36	4.85
					N 13.27	13.59
5. 2-Methoxy		106	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	C 47.68	48.00
					H 4.08	4.62
					N 12.76	12.92
6. 4-Methoxy		112	50	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	C 47.82	48.00
					H 4.36	4.62
					N 12.80	12.92
7. 2-Ethoxy		112	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	C 48.94	49.56
					H 4.86	5.01
					N 12.44	12.39

